

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 2.2.2: Delivery of protocols (lab scale) ready to scale up the production of the new high value material (in collaboration with Companies)

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	From M 8 to M 28
Periodic report date and version:	16/02/2025, Ver_1
Deliverable RM2 Responsible	UPO
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material)	PU	M30	
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material)	PU	M30	
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material)	PU	M32	

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	
D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	

A) INTRODUCTION

The partners involved in the D 2.2.2 (essentially related to the activities listed in Sub-Task 2.2.1) worked with the aim to develop and describe different protocols ready to be scaled-up, (also in collaboration with Companies interested to share the research of RM2-GRIP). The corresponding Milestones (M2.2.2. + M2.4.2) reported the schematic description of the workflow.

ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of partners was distributed depending on i) the matrix and ii) the facilities availability, allowing to obtain different protocols and methods for the upcycling of the raw material previously chemically characterized. Each partner used different technologies, combining them when possible and/or feasible, obtaining the selection the best performing processes here described. Anyway, further optimization of the workflows will be possible, particularly considering the scale-up of at least three process in collaboration with Companies.

EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The overall work was related to the selection of some best-performing methods able to valorize and up-cycle principally the four materials considered for the upcycling:

1. Nervine foods by-products and wastes (cocoa bean shells and spent coffee)
2. Rice by products
3. Fruit pomace (apple)
4. Cow whey.

The Environment Park partner, beside the material selected as target, developed some additional protocols aimed to valorize tomato by-products, as following described.

The combination of some performing green and bio-based techniques (allowing to reduce the impact on the environment, first avoiding to use organic solvents for the extractions) was optimized, leading to reach the optimization of 10 different protocols/methods, as described in Milestones 2.2.2. and 2.4.2.

A maximum of 4 protocols will be accurately selected among the ten protocols described in this Deliverable 2.2.2., as methods ready for the scale-up of the processes, considering different parameters: i) the availability of the raw material to be processed; ii) the usefulness of the techniques allowing to valorize the raw material and iii) the possible collaboration with

Companies regarding both a) the recovery of the unprocessed material and b) the processing of the thereof, leading to some ingredients/model products (nutraceuticals, cosmeceuticals, food, industrial applications) at pre-competitive scaled pilot level. These methods will be also considered for a LCA evaluation, in order to estimate the feasibility/applicability of these process as new potential source of high value products in different area (chemical, pharmaceutical, nutraceutical/cosmetical, industrial, environmental).

DSF-UPO

1. Process for the valorization of cocoa bean shells (CBSs) fibers via US-Enzyme driven upcycling:

▪ Description of the process/method

The treatment developed and selected for the scale-up consists in a sequential US treatment followed by an enzymatic hydrolysis using a commercial cellulase mixture to hydrolyze the dietary fiber fraction. Briefly, 50 grams of raw non-defatted CBSs were dissolved in 500 mL citrate buffer 50mmol/L. and pre-treated with US. The use of the enzymes lead to the improvement of the extraction of polyphenols fraction and to the depolymerization of the fiber fraction, allowing to release potential prebiotic oligosaccharides.

- US treatment

Sonication was performed before the enzymatic hydrolysis, utilizing an Hielscher 400ST with a 14 mm titanium sonotrode. Different parameters will be tested for sonication. Continuous and pulsed sonication for 10, 20 and 30 min. and amplitudes of 50 - 100 %, respectively, were considered, monitoring the temperature during the process. The sampling will be carried out at the end of each sonications and chromatographic analysis of the main bioactive polyphenols (LC-MS/MS) and oligosaccharides (HPLC-RID) will be conducted. The best performing conditions for cocoa treatment was achieved through a 20 minutes continuous sonication at 50 % of amplitude.

-Enzymatic hydrolysis

After the optimization of the US treatment, a subsequent enzymatic hydrolysis will be conducted. The temperature of the batch mixture (cocoa bean extract in buffer after US

processing) must be increased to 30 °C and, successively a commercial blend of cellulolytic enzymes is added to the batch (Disca et al., 2024). This batch has been incubated for a total ofhours, with sampling carried out every hour for chromatographic analysis of the main bioactive polyphenols (LC-MS/MS) and oligosaccharides (HPLC-RID), as reported Jaouhari et al., (2024). At the end of the enzymatic hydrolysis, enzymes activity is stopped with a rapid heat-shock at 80 °C for 5 min.

-Separation and purification

The supernatant was separated from the pellets through a filter cloth and directly spray-dried, while the exhaust pellet was dried in an oven at 40 °C (overnight), and the dried pellet processed in a ball mill. The limited temperature were considered in order to limit the polyphenols oxidation. The so obtained fractions are rich in polyphenols and fibers with prebiotic properties, as reported in some publications.

This process (focused on the valorization of CBSs, allowing both polyphenol-rich powders and prebiotic-rich oligosaccharides) will be scaled up producing new performing ingredients for food supplements and/or cosmetic products.

NB: *The conditions here described will probably be further optimized collaborating with the company that will cooperate to the scale up as well as to the design and formulation of the food supplement prepared with this ingredients, as foreseen by the research program.*

REF.

Disca, V., Capuano, E., & Arlorio, M. (2024). Colonic fermentation of enzymatically treated cocoa bean shells (CBSs) and short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) production. *LWT*, 116311.

Jaouhari, Y., Ferreira-Santos, P., Disca, V., Oliveira, H., Martoccia, M., Travaglia, F., ... & Bordiga, M. (2024). Carbohydrases treatment on blueberry pomace: Influence on chemical composition and bioactive potential. *LWT*, 206, 116573.

▪ **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The added value of the process is related to the complete elimination of the organic solvent/alcohols during the extraction, reducing the impact on the environment. Moreover, considering the high number of the strategies focused on the recovery of high value material from CBSs published during the last ten years, the originality could be correlated with the exhaustive recovery and up-cycling of material (i) polyphenol-rich powder and ii) prebiotic oligosaccharides-rich fiber) from the matrix. The prebiotic capacity has been confirmed by production of short chain fatty acids in batch fermentation using gut microbiota isolated from a healthy donor (data not reported).

▪ **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material**

obtained and its potential use)

New process for the up-cycling of cocoa bean shells, allowing to obtain two valorized ingredients for food supplements and cosmetic products (polyphenol-rich powder and prebiotic-rich fiber).

2. Process for the valorization of apple pomace US-Enzyme driven upcycling:

▪ Description of the process/method

The treatment consists in a heat assisted extraction (HAE) performed in a water vessel under shaking control (batch process). The solvent used for the extraction is pure water in order to obtain an extract ready to use without the need to remove organic solvent in trace (e.g. methanol). For this purpose, apple pomace (obtained from cold pressed apple juice production) was first subjected to a drying and milling process, to obtain a matrix as homogeneous as possible. The process was optimized starting from the protocol reported in Reis et. al, 2012.

- Heat assisted extraction

Briefly, based on previous studies (Reis F. et al., 2012), pure distilled water was used as solvent. In order to find the best parameters of extraction, the influence of temperature (in the range from 35 to 80 °C), solvent/material ratio (S/L ratio; 0.1-0.025 g mL⁻¹) and time (from 15 to 60 min) were considered. The best performing outcome were selected employing mathematical models (ANNs, RSM, RFs). More particularly, using Random Forests algorithm, a temperature, solvent/material ratio and time of 80 °C, 0.1 g mL⁻¹ and 60 min, respectively, were identify as optimal conditions for the extraction of phlorizin from the raw material.

- Separation and purification

The extract obtained has been subjected to a centrifugation process (4 °C, 9.000 rpm, 10 min), followed by a filtration step. The analytical identification/quantification of the target molecules (polyphenols) by LC-MS/MS and HPLC-DAD required the application of a SPME (Solid Phase Micro Extraction) for the clean-up of the processed samples. After quantification of the bioactive compounds of interest, the supernatant was spray-dried and freeze-dried, leading to a stable powder rich in polyphenols as well as characterized by antioxidant properties.

NB: *The conditions here described will probably be further optimized collaborating with the company that will cooperate to the scale up as well as to the design and formulation of the food supplement prepared with this ingredients, as foreseen by the research program.*

REF.

Reis, S.F.; Rai, D.K.; Abu-Ghannam, N. Water at room temperature as a solvent for the extraction of apple pomace phenolic compounds. *Food Chemistry*, 2012, 135.3: 1991-1998.

▪ **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The added value of the process, based on a green extraction using water, is principally related to the application of AI-based techniques to select the best conditions of extraction. Different approaches were compared (several non-supervised and supervised Artificial Neural Networks, Response Surface Methodology, Random Forests). Random Forest permitted to obtain the best performing outcome, leading to a powerful tool to identify the best performing parameters for the optimization of the extraction of each polyphenol compounds from apple pomace.

▪ **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

The principal outcome reached was the set-up of a green method to extract with water polyphenols-rich and phlorizin-rich extracts from apple pomace, allowing to obtain new powdered ingredients both characterized by antioxidant property and bioactivity (related to the phlorizin content). These ingredients will be used together with the prebiotic fiber from CBSs for the scale up of a pilot production of food supplements.

ENVIRONMENT PARK

3: Process for the valorization of apple via steam explosion pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis extraction

▪ **Description of the process/method**

APPLE STEAM EXPLOSION PRETREATMENT

The treatment pressure is 23 bar, the pressure holding phase lasts 10 minutes, and the saturated steam temperature is 220 °C. The weight of the input sample is 4.93 kg.

After preheating the system to the temperature set for the test, the biomass was manually fed into the steam explosion reactor, trying to minimize material losses.

The reactor was raised in 6.3 minutes from the starting pressure (1 bar) to the desired conditions for the process: mean 23.5 bar and 218.9 °C, for 5 minutes. The final weight of the material after treatment was 9.7348 kg

APPLE ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

The objective of enzymatic pretreatment was to study the degradation of plant cell wall components and to identify and quantify total polyphenols and total flavonoids at a later stage. For the analysis, 4 samples were prepared: the first sample containing the blank, the second with the cellulase enzyme inside, the third with the cellulase and xylanase enzymes inside, and the last with the cellulase and pectinase enzymes inside.

The protocol for enzymatic hydrolysis was as follows:

-Preparation of 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 5.0.

Two solutions were used for preparation: solution A consisting of 0.1 M citric acid stock and solution B consisting of 0.1 M sodium citrate stock. 410 mL of solution A and 590 mL of solution B were mixed. The pH was measured and raised to 5 with NaOH (to raise the pH) or KCl (to lower the pH).

-Thawing and grinding of biomass.

-Mixing the biomass with enzymes, citrate buffer and the distilled water. The contents were placed inside falcons whose final volume is 200 mL.

-Incubation at 50°C and set to agitation at 150 rpm.

- Sampling (as timings were taken at t0 and after 5,20, 24 and 29 h) and freezing.

From each Falcon, 30 mL was taken and the samples were placed in the freezer before being sent to the appropriate laboratories for further analysis.

SOLID/LIQUID SEPARATION AND PURIFICATION

Following the extraction phase, a solid/liquid separation was performed using a 20-litre pneumatic press with a cloth filter to obtain a homogeneous solution. This reduced the amount of solids in the solution to be used in the next step of membrane purification. Solid particles are responsible for the phenomenon of fouling, which reduces the filtering capacity of the membrane.

At last, purification was performed using a tangential filtration machine.

▪ **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The processes selected for the treatment of this biomass are characterized by their environmental sustainability.

Steam explosion pre-treatment has advantages over other methods, particularly chemical pre-treatment, which often uses environmentally harmful solvents that are difficult to dispose of. Steam explosion is therefore considered to be one of the most environmentally

friendly and cost-effective methods that can be used, as it uses only steam and a small amount of water (about 1.5 kg of water per kg of biomass treated) (Hoang et al., 2023). Pressurised superheated water behaves as an excellent solvent, without the toxicity limitations typical of chemical pretreatment, and uses less energy.

Extraction of valuable compounds by enzymatic hydrolysis also has advantages over chemical extractions (Singh et al., 2024): it operates under conditions close to ambient temperature and pressure, allows operation on specific substrates and enables precise extraction of target molecules. In this way, it is possible to obtain high value products from lignocellulosic matrices that would otherwise be wasted, with low energy consumption and low environmental impact.

REF.

- Anh Tuan Hoang, Xuan Phuong Nguyen, Xuan Quang Duong, Ümit Ağbulut, Christophe Len, Phuoc Quy Phong Nguyen, Mohamed Kchaou, Wei-Hsin Chen, Steam explosion as sustainable biomass pretreatment technique for biofuel production: Characteristics and challenges, *Bioresource Technology*, Volume 385, 2023, 129398, ISSN 0960-8524, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2023.129398>.

- Rajat Singh, Rajul Jain, Priyanka Soni, Sergio de los Santos-Villalobos, Sourav Chattaraj, Deblina Roy, Debasis Mitra, Ashish Gaur, Graphing the Green route: Enzymatic hydrolysis in sustainable decomposition, *Current Research in Microbial Sciences*, Volume 7, 2024, 100281, ISSN 2666-5174, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmicr.2024.100281>.

▪ **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

Several molecules of interest have been extracted from apples, including p-coumaric acid, phlorizin, quercetin and rutin. These molecules have an antioxidant action and may find application in cosmetic and nutraceutical products.

4. Process for the valorization of tomato via steam explosion pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis extraction (this matrix was not selected for the scale -up process, but processed by Environment Park Partner during the research in order to evaluate and set up the green techniques).

▪ **Description of the process/method**

TOMATO STEAM EXPLOSION PRETREATMENT

The treatment pressure is 15 bar, the pressure holding phase lasts 5 minutes, and the saturated steam temperature is 195.2 °C. The weight of the input sample is 13.9 kg.

After preheating the system to the temperature set for the test, the biomass was manually fed into the steam explosion reactor, trying to minimize material losses.

The reactor was raised in 4 minutes from the starting pressure (1 bar) to the desired conditions for the process: mean 15.4 bar and 196.4 °C, for 6 minutes. The final weight of the material after treatment was 17.0536 kg.

TOMATO ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

The objective of enzymatic pretreatment was to study the degradation of plant cell wall components and to identify and quantify total polyphenols and total flavonoids at a later stage. For the analysis, 4 samples were prepared: the first sample containing the blank, the second with the cellulase enzyme inside, the third with the cellulase and xylanase enzymes inside, and the last with the cellulase and pectinase enzymes inside. Two types of tomatoes were employed: cherry tomatoes and salad tomatoes.

The protocol for enzymatic hydrolysis was as follows:

-Preparation of 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 5.0.

Two solutions were used for preparation: solution A consisting of 0.1 M citric acid stock and solution B consisting of 0.1 M sodium citrate stock. 410 mL of solution A and 590 mL of solution B were mixed. The pH was measured and raised to 5 with NaOH (to raise the pH) or KCl (to lower the pH).

-Thawing and grinding of biomass.

-Mixing the biomass with enzymes, citrate buffer and the distilled water. The contents were placed inside falcons whose final volume is 200 mL.

-Incubation at 50°C and set to agitation at 150 rpm.

- Sampling (as timings were taken at t0 and after 5,20, 24 and 29 h) and freezing.

From each Falcon, 30 mL was taken and the samples were placed in the freezer before being sent to the appropriate laboratories for further analysis.

SOLID/LIQUID SEPARATION AND PURIFICATION

Following the extraction phase, a solid/liquid separation was performed using a 20-litre pneumatic press with a cloth filter to obtain a homogeneous solution. This reduced the amount of solids in the solution to be used in the next step of membrane purification. Solid particles are responsible for the phenomenon of fouling, which reduces the filtering capacity of the membrane.

At last, purification was performed using a tangential filtration machine.

▪ **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The added value as well as the originality is comparable to the facts reported previously in case study 3.

REF.

- Anh Tuan Hoang, Xuan Phuong Nguyen, Xuan Quang Duong, Ümit Ağbulut, Christophe Len, Phuoc Quy Phong Nguyen, Mohamed Kchaou, Wei-Hsin Chen, Steam explosion as sustainable biomass pretreatment technique for biofuel production: Characteristics and challenges, *Bioresource Technology*, Volume 385, 2023, 129398, ISSN 0960-8524, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2023.129398>.

- Rajat Singh, Rajul Jain, Priyanka Soni, Sergio de los Santos-Villalobos, Sourav Chattaraj, Deblina Roy, Debasis Mitra, Ashish Gaur, Graphing the Green route: Enzymatic hydrolysis in sustainable decomposition, *Current Research in Microbial Sciences*, Volume 7, 2024, 100281, ISSN 2666-5174, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmicr.2024.100281>.

▪ **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

Numerous antioxidant molecules have been extracted from tomatoes, such as vitamin C, beta-carotene and flavonoids. Prominent among these is lycopene, a molecule with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity, which can be used in cosmetics and nutraceuticals.

5. Process for the valorization of spent coffee via steam explosion pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis extraction

▪ Description of the process/method

COFFE STEAM EXPLOSION PRETREATMENT

The treatment pressure is 8 bar, the pressure holding phase lasts 20 minutes, and the saturated steam temperature is 150 °C. The weight of the input sample is 7.5 kg.

After preheating the system to the temperature set for the test, the biomass was manually fed into the steam explosion reactor, trying to minimize material losses.

The reactor was raised in 1.03 minutes from the starting pressure (1 bar) to the desired conditions for the process: mean 8.2 bar and 168.5 °C, for 20 minutes. The final weight of the material after treatment was 13.4587 kg.

COFFE ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

The objective of enzymatic pretreatment was to identify and quantify total polyphenols and total flavonoids present in the matrix and after the steam explosion process. For the analysis, 2 samples were: the first sample containing the blank and the second with the cellulase+xylanase enzyme inside (NS22086).

The protocol for enzymatic hydrolysis was as follows:

-Preparation of 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 5.0.

Two solutions were used for preparation: solution A consisting of 0.1 M citric acid stock and solution B consisting of 0.1 M sodium citrate stock. 410 mL of solution A and 590 mL of solution B were mixed. The pH was measured and raised to 5 with NaOH (to raise the pH) or KCl (to lower the pH).

-Thawing and grinding of biomass.

-Mixing the biomass with enzymes, citrate buffer and the distilled water. The contents were placed inside falcons whose final volume is 250 mL.

-Incubation at 50°C and set to agitation at 150 rpm.

- Sampling (as timings were taken at t0 and after 5,20, 24 and 29 h) and freezing.

From each Falcon, 30 mL was taken and the samples were placed in the freezer before being sent to the appropriate laboratories for further analysis.

SOLID/LIQUID SEPARATION AND PURIFICATION

Following the extraction phase, a solid/liquid separation was performed using a 20-litre pneumatic press with a cloth filter to obtain a homogeneous solution. This reduced the

amount of solids in the solution to be used in the next step of membrane purification. Solid particles are responsible for the phenomenon of fouling, which reduces the filtering capacity of the membrane.

At last, purification was performed using a tangential filtration machine.

▪ **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The added value as well as the originality is comparable to the facts reported previously in case study 4.

▪ **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

From spent coffee, it is possible to extract substances of interest such as chlorogenic acid, caffeine and, in general, molecules belonging to the polyphenols. In smaller quantities, palmitic and linoleic acid can also be extracted.

6. Process for the valorization of cocoa bean husk via steam explosion pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis extraction

- **Description of the process/method**

COCOA STEAM EXPLOSION PRETREATMENT

The treatment pressure is 8 bar, the duration of the pressure holding phase is 20 minutes, and the saturated steam temperature is 150 °C. The weight of the input sample is 2.54 kg.

After preheating the system to the temperature set for the test, the biomass was manually fed into the steam explosion reactor, trying to minimize material losses.

The reactor was raised in 0.7 minutes from the starting pressure (1 bar) to the desired conditions for the process: mean 8.1 bar and 167.8078 °C, for 20 minutes. The final weight of the material after treatment was 6.2342 kg.

COCOA ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

The objective of enzymatic pretreatment was to identify and quantify total polyphenols and total flavonoids present in the matrix and after the steam explosion process. For the analysis, 3 samples were prepared: the first sample containing the blank, the second with the cellulase + xylanase enzyme inside (NS22086) and the last sample contain xylanase enzyme inside.

The protocol for enzymatic hydrolysis was as follows:

- Preparation of 0.1 M citrate buffer at pH 5.0.

Two solutions were used for preparation: solution A consisting of 0.1 M citric acid stock and solution B consisting of 0.1 M sodium citrate stock. 410 mL of solution A and 590 mL of solution B were mixed. The pH was measured and raised to 5 with NaOH (to raise the pH) or KCl (to lower the pH).

- Thawing and grinding of biomass.

- Mixing the biomass with enzymes, citrate buffer and the distilled water. The contents were placed inside falcons whose final volume is 250 mL.

- Incubation at 50°C and set to agitation at 150 rpm.

- Sampling (as timings were taken at t0 and after 5,20, 24 and 29 h) and freezing.

From each Falcon, 30 mL was taken and the samples were placed in the freezer before being sent to the appropriate laboratories for further analysis.

SOLID/LIQUID SEPARATION AND PURIFICATION

Following the extraction phase, a solid/liquid separation was performed using a 20-litre pneumatic press with a cloth filter to obtain a homogeneous solution. This reduced the amount of solids in the solution to be used in the next step of membrane purification. Solid particles are responsible for the phenomenon of fouling, which reduces the filtering capacity of the membrane.

At last, purification was performed using a tangential filtration machine.

- **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The added value as well as the originality is comparable to the facts reported previously in case study 5.

- **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

The samples were sent to UPO partner for further analysis and characterization, especially to compare the outcome obtained with the parallel method described in DSF-UPO section.

7. ENVI: process for the valorization of rice husks via steam explosion pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis extraction

▪ Description of the process/method

RICE HUSKS STEAM EXPLOSION PRETREATMENT

The treatment pressure is 15 bar, the pressure holding phase lasts 5 minutes, and the saturated steam temperature is 150 °C. The weight of the input sample is 1,5 kg.

After preheating the system to the temperature set for the test, the biomass was manually fed into the steam explosion reactor, trying to minimize material losses.

The reactor was raised in 1 minute from the starting pressure (1 bar) to the desired conditions for the process: mean 15 bar and 195,2 °C, for 5 minutes. The final weight of the material after treatment was 6,1220 kg.

RICE HUSKS ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

This treatment is planned.

▪ Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment

The added value as well as the originality is comparable to the facts reported previously in case study 6.

▪ Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)

The samples were sent to UPO for further analysis

UNIPV

8. Process for the valorization of rice husk (with/without pre-treatment) and used cooking oil by biocatalysis

- Description of the process/method

A fully biocatalytic approach was developed for the synthesis of sugar fatty acid esters (SFAE) starting from different renewable feedstocks: rice husk served as the source for the polar head of the surfactants, while refined used cooking oil was employed for the synthesis of the apolar tail. Rice husk was used, either directly or following one of two distinct pre-treatment processes, as biomass in the trans-glycosylation reaction in 1-BuOH catalyzed by cellulases. The cellulose fraction of rice husk was hydrolyzed by endo- and exo-glucanases contained in the cellulase cocktail, while the β -glucosidases catalyzed the trans-glycosylation reaction affording the polar head in 50% yield p/p. Refined used cooking oil was trans-esterified with EtOH by a commercially available immobilized lipase obtaining the corresponding fatty acids ethyl esters (70% yield). The glucose-based polar head and the ethyl ester-based apolar tails were submitted to the enzymatic transesterification reaction catalyzed by a commercially available immobilized lipase to obtain the corresponding SFAE (72% yield).

- Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment

Rice husk can be used directly as raw material in enzymatic bio-transformations under mild reaction conditions (40 °C and optimum pH of enzymes around 5.5). The pretreatments tested did not allow an increase in the conversion, so they will not be taken into further consideration, thus skipping an additional step requiring the use of high temperature and organic solvents/chemical reactants.

- Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)

The SFAE obtained are non-ionic surfactants. Compared to other classes of surfactants, SFAE are fully biodegradable and thus not harmful for aquatic marine environment, they are non-irritating, they are tasteless and odorless and are therefore of great interest for food industry and personal care products, especially for infancy.

Furthermore, by controlling the degree of esterification and the nature of sugar and fatty acid residues, the hydrophilic-lipophilic balances (HLB) of SFAE can be fine-tuned and thus customized for a specific application.

9. Process for the valorization of cheese whey permeate and used cooking oil by biocatalysis

- Description of the process/method

The bio-based synthesis of sugar fatty acid esters (SFAE) was carried out through a fully biocatalytic process by using different renewable feedstock: cheese whey permeate was utilized for the synthesis of the polar head of the surfactants, while refined used cooking oil provided the apolar tail. Cheese whey permeate was directly submitted to a trans-glycosylation reaction in 1-BuOH catalyzed by a β -galactosidase immobilized in house. Reaction conditions were optimized (homogeneous/biphasic system; CWP concentration, CWP: 1-BuOH ratio) to achieve high reaction conversion and streamline the work-up procedure. The process was scaled-up (200 mL of CWP) affording 7 g of the galactose-based polar head after liquid-liquid extraction. Refined used cooking oil was trans-esterified with bio-EtOH by a commercially available immobilized lipase obtaining the corresponding fatty acid ethyl esters (60% yield). The enzymatic transesterification reaction between the galactose-based polar head and the ethyl ester-based apolar tail is under investigation (reaction optimization) to obtain the target SFAE. In parallel, the trans-glycosylation reaction catalyzed by β -galactosidase is currently under study to develop site-directed variants of the enzyme (targeting surface amino acid residues) to promote protein immobilization and, in turn, a more efficient biocatalytic process. To this aim, recombinant β -galactosidases will be produced using *Kluyveromyces lactis* as heterologous system and site-directed mutagenesis will be aimed at replacing some surface residues with specific amino acids that mediate the binding to the immobilization matrix.

- Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment
Cheese whey permeate without any pretreatment was directly used as raw material in an enzymatic biotransformation (liter scale) under mild reaction conditions (40 °C, pH 4.0). Purification of the desired product has been optimized in order to avoid tedious and expensive chromatographic steps.
- Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)

SFAE composed of galactose-based polar heads and fatty acid apolar tails were obtained. SFAE are valuable non-ionic surfactants. Compared to other classes of surfactants, SFAE are fully biodegradable and thus not harmful for aquatic marine environment, they are non-irritating, they are tasteless and odorless and are therefore of great interest for food industry and personal care products, especially for infancy. Furthermore, by controlling the degree of esterification and the nature of sugar and fatty acid residues, the hydrophilic-lipophilic balances (HLB) of SFAE can be fine-tuned and thus customized for a specific application.

POLITO

10. Process for the valorization of apple pomace via Ultrasound-assisted-extraction (UAE) and Microwave-assisted- extraction (MAE) using water as solvent

- **Description of the process/method**

The research explores extracting polyphenols from apple pomace using 2 different physical methods:

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE): This method uses ultrasound waves to disrupt the apple pomace cell walls and enhance the release of polyphenols into the water.

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE): This method uses microwaves to heat the water and apple pomace, accelerating the extraction process.

The research uses water as the solvent because it is considered a green solvent, non-toxic,

renewable, safe, and easy to handle.

For each method, the researchers conducted screening experiments to determine the best extraction conditions. They varied the solid-to-liquid ratio, temperature (for TSE and UAE) or power (for MAE). They then conducted kinetic experiments to evaluate the optimal extraction time for each method

- **Added value/originality of the process regarding the state of the art/impact on the environment**

The research provides a sustainable way to utilize apple pomace, a significant by-product of the apple juice industry often discarded and causing pollution. Extracting polyphenols transforms this waste into valuable ingredients. The use of water as a solvent is environmentally friendly compared to conventional solvents such as alcohols and acetone, which are typically used for polyphenol extraction. This choice of solvent makes the process more sustainable and reduces human health and environmental risks. The comparison of UAE, and MAE allows for a comprehensive evaluation of each method's efficiency and environmental impact. While UAE and MAE have been previously studied, this research directly compares these methods for apple pomace polyphenol extraction to determine the most effective and sustainable option

- **Principal outcomes reached (description of the ingredient/molecule/material obtained and its potential use)**

MAE is the most efficient and environmentally friendly method for extracting polyphenols from apple pomace. MAE produces the highest yield in less time than UAE.

The extracted polyphenols have potential applications in various products due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and immune-modulating properties:

Cosmetics: Polyphenols can protect skin from UV damage and promote skin health.

Nutraceuticals: Polyphenols and their health benefits can be incorporated into food supplements and functional foods.

Pharmaceuticals: Polyphenols are being investigated for their potential in treating various health conditions.

This research contributes to a circular economy by demonstrating the feasibility of extracting polyphenols from apple pomace using environmentally friendly methods. The process offers a solution for apple waste management while producing valuable ingredients for multiple industries.

Final considerations and perspectives

The activity here described was primarily directed to identify the best performing methods/process useful to 1. upcycle the raw material (by products from different animal and plant material/foods) and 2. to permit the following scale up of some selected performing processes.

This part of the research allowed to obtain 10 process (exploiting combining bio-based and green processes), leading to new high value molecules/ingredients for different applications (food, chemical, cosmetic, industrial, pharmaceutical) as foreseen by the original project description and aim.

At least three combined methods will be selected to be scaled up in collaboration with some Companies.